

Abstract

Survey of Primary Health Care Facility Readiness Assessment for Cervical Cancer Prevention in Bauchi North: Implications for Policy Makers

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Background: Reducing the menace of cervical cancer through effective healthcare delivery services requires the availability of adequate infrastructure, screening and diagnostic medical facilities, adequate/uninterrupted drug supply chain, well-motivated and proficiently trained medical personnel at all levels. The study aimed to determine the facility readiness for cervical cancer prevention in Bauchi North Senatorial District.

Materials and Methods: It was a cross-sectional descriptive study of 36 PHCCs in 3 randomly selected LGAs in the state. The WHO service delivery indicator (SDI) form for cervical cancer

facility readiness was used for the data collection and analysed with descriptive statistics.

Results: There were 237,627 women eligible for cervical cancer screening and 230 healthcare workers. The overall facility readiness score was 0.67, which falls within the WHO red line (0.0 – 0.99 red; 1.0 – 1.79 yellow; and 1.8 – 2.0 green). Service utilisation and staffing scores were zero ($\leq 75\%$). Enabling environment/infrastructure, procurement and supply scored 1.61 and 1.34, respectively. However, equipment, supplies, and medicines specifically related to testing/screening were zero. Infection prevention score was 1.58, data management and quality 0.82, while Policies and guidelines readiness score was zero, as there was any towards screening and treatment. Referral mechanisms for frank cervical cancer score were 0.67. Surprisingly, almost all the facilities were offering HPV vaccination to the target adolescent population, which is the primary strategy for cervical cancer prevention.

Conclusion: The facility readiness score of 0.67 left much to be desired, as they did not fulfil at least 75% of the standards.

Keywords: Facility, readiness, cervical cancer, screening

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